
MANAGEMENT OF ACADEMIC LIBRARY AND INFORMATION CENTERS IN THE 21ST CENTURY

Mr. Rahul Hanmant Kulkarni

Librarian, Shri. Shivaji Mahavidyalya, Barshi

Corresponding Author - Mr. Rahul Hanmant Kulkarni

Email-Kulkarnirahul555@gmail.com

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Abstract:

Today we are living in digital age, or now we are living in techno age. In six month there is new invention in all the technical things. When we expert in one technology there is new and added technologies for that there is challenge for everyone who faces technology. When we compare with library there is also new challenges for library services. In some extent we see that Library Automation and E-Security are the new advanced things. For librarian he should manage all the things. In Academic libraries most of the Librarian facing problem of management. When we evaluate work there are various parameters and test to solve problem.

Management is the art of getting things done by a group of people with the effective utilization of available resources. An introduction cannot be treated as a managing body running any organization. A minimum of two persons are essential to form a management. These persons perform the function in order to achieve the objectives of an organization.

Def: Peter Drucker:- “Management is an organ, organs can be described and defined only through their functions.”

F.W.Taylor:- “Management is the art of knowing what you want to do and then seeing that it is done in the best & cheapest way.”

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Introduction:

In Library there are various users. Many people get best services from Library. But few of them they are not get yet best service or they are not satisfied. There are also two way problem one is from user that they are mum. The library staff can't understand their need. And also reverse is happened to user. In all manner there are some skills to know the users need in short period. For this the library staff having a skill. In library management all the goals of the library are related with library staff with the help from them the library become rich. In all manner Librarian is the apex of all the techniques

that are used when there is new technique implies the librarian is having skill to participate all the staff in that process. There is also training for him to do such things.

Library Management is a sub-discipline of institutional management that focuses on specific issues faced by libraries and library management professionals. Library management encompasses normal management tasks as well as intellectual freedom, anti-censorship, and fundraising tasks. Issues faced in library management frequently overlap those faced in management of nonprofit organization.

Basic tasks in Library Management include:

1. Planning the acquisition of Materials;
2. Negotiating Interlibrary loan (ILL);
3. Stacks maintenance;
4. Oversee fee collection;
5. Membership management;
6. Responding to challenges;
7. Event Planning;
8. Fundraising;
9. Manage human resources.

Planning and Maintaining Library Facilities:

An important aspect of library management is planning and maintain library facilities. Planning the construction of new libraries or remodeling those that exist is internal as user need are often changing. To supplement their operating budget, managers often secure funding through gifts and fund raising. Many facilities are also including cafes', friends of the library, and exhibit spaces to help generate additional revenue. These venues must be taken into account when planning for building expansions. The site for new construction must be designed, constructed and then evaluated. Once established, it is important that the building management keep up on regular maintenance. This can also be completed by delegating tasks to maintenance personal or hiring as outside company through bids.

A well established library is essential for any academic institution. As a focal point for teaching, learning and research, it is expected to provide standard information resources. Today, academic libraries are struggling to keep their place as the major source of inquiry in the face of emerging digital technology. Digital technology has revolutionized not only the way information packed, processed, stored

and disseminated, but also how users seek and access information,. Academic libraries no longer restrict themselves to print services such as collection development, cataloguing and classification, circulation and reference services, current awareness, selective dissemination and other bibliographic services, but have extended their efforts to interdisciplinary concepts and computer software and hardware and telecommunication engineering and technology. As observed by Campbell (2006:17), "numerous creative and useful services have evolved within academic libraries in the digital age: providing quality learning spaces, creating metadata, offering virtual ref. services, teaching information Literacy, choosing resources and managing resource licenses, collecting and digitizing archival materials, and maintain digital repositories." Academic Libraries presently are faced with not only the decision on what books and journals to acquire to satisfy faculty and students but also as how to remain relevant in the digital era, mindful of low budgets and resentment on the part of institutional administrators.

Importance of Management:

1. Management meet the challenge of change.
2. Accomplishment of group goals.
3. Effective utilization of library services;
4. Effective functioning of services;
5. Resource Development;
6. Sound organization structure;
7. Management directs the organization;
8. Integrates various interest;
9. Stability;
10. Innovation;
11. Co-ordination and team sprit;
12. Tacking Problems;

13. A Tool for personality development;

Scientific Management:

In the 18th Century, the production was affected by industrial revolution, When the management people wanted to increase their production. Their ambitions were fulfilled by the invention of the concept of Scientific management by F.W. Taylor in the 19th century. Taylor is the first person to find the concept of scientific management and develop it so he is called the father of Science of Management.

F.W. Taylor defined scientific management as the substitution of exact scientific investigation and knowledge for the old individual judgment of opinion; either of the workmen or the boss, in all matters relating to the work done in the establishment.

Principles of Scientific Management:

1. Harmony in group action;
2. Co.operation;
3. Maximum Output;
4. Improvement of workers.
5. Science not rule of thumb;

Elements or Features of Scientific Management:

1. Separation of planning from executive functions;
2. Scientific task settings;
3. Functional foremanship;
4. Work study;
5. Methods Study;
6. Motion Duty;
7. Time Study;
8. Fatigue Study;
9. Rate Setting;
10. Standardization;
11. Scientific selection and training;
12. Financial incentives;
13. Mental revolution;
14. Economy.

Management thought was developed due to contribution of many intellectuals who have different background. These contributions have not

been suitably and adequately integrated to give a unified theory of management.

In total library management there are some newly services that are really good for library. i.e.

- Free access to the internet;
 - Providing reference information to support educational achievement and personal development.
 - Conducting library tours that support self – sufficiency and comfort level in using the library.
 - Training for literacy and information finding skills. Using both print and electronic resources.
 - Offering readers advisory services for individuals and groups.
 - Encouraging the use of the collection in all formats.
 - Providing finding aids and other supporting materials.
 - Facilitating access to resources outside the collection when necessary, such as referrals and inter library loans.
 - Cooperating with other information and service providers in the community.
 - Providing services to special groups such as young adults with disabilities, teen parents and teens who may be incarcerated or unable to come to the library for a variety of reasons.
- The library is having various types of user the librarian should have to follow the following programmers. And living in the 21st century we are in digital platform.
1. Books talks, Storytelling, and Book Promotion;
 2. Organise and give information of book exhibition through facebook page of library.
 3. With the help of college website we can gave a call to n

- number of students to attend the elocution competition.
4. Twitter is also a landmark option for various users.
 5. Performance of a cultural nature such as music, art, and drama.
 6. Co-operative programming with community institutions and groups.
 7. Young adult production (drama, publication, Tv, video). A longing to their ages the library should arrange various programmes.
 8. Workshops designed to teach a skill for creative expression.
 9. Reading debates.
 10. Book Promotion.
 11. Arrange a book show: “Best Books in a month” to user via zoom application. So they can see it.
 12. Play a youtube channel of college library and run various activities in a year.
 13. Arrange a foreign speaker to gave a lecture to our user via virtual application.

Quality Assurance in Higher Education:

Quality Assurance has become a global issue in higher education, especially with the economic and technological growth in the wake of globalization in addition to the increasing mobility and accessibility of e-learning

Information Centres:

There is small use in selling up war information centre unless people know it is there. And to reach the regular habituates of the library is not enough. The chief secondary value of the centre is that it brings many new users to the library, people who are not natural readers and who now learn for the first time that the library can be of help to them.

An information centre is defined as an organization that selects, acquires, stores and retrieves information in response to requests, indexes of information, and disseminates information in anticipation and in response requests.

There are varied forms of information centres eq.

1. **Information Analysis Centres:** An Organisation which selects, acquire stores, and retrieves specific information in response to request; announces, abstracts, extracts, indexes information and disseminates information from document to in response to or in anticipation.
2. **Clearing Houses:** It is a central agency where information is collected, classify and distribute, specially information.
3. **Data centres and data Banks**

Construction Management:

Alternatives to the traditional design/bid/build approach for the construction o libraries are increasingly used both to improve design and to manage cost. With a design / build option, the library contracts with a developer or construction management firm that can provide both desing and constructional services. While this can offer advanced in both schedule and cost control, it somewhat removes the client from design decision since the architect is employed by the developer or CM firm.

Another increasingly popular approach is Construction Management at Risk model, in which the library contracts with both the architect and the building contractor through RFP processes and employs a program manager to coordinate their interaction and oversee the building project with this approach, all project partners remain directly accountable to the client.

A major advantage of the desining/ build and the alternatives is the involvement of the building contractor early in the project desing, which allows more effective cost engineering to keep the project within budget.

Role of Librarian in Management:

In Library the post of Librarian is the apex post from which all the activity should be done. In management there are various things that should be not ignored. Every staff member has their own esteem. When we chart the work diagram Librarian should aware all the keen aspect of the thing. In that case the librarian taking some tricks. In many big academic colleges the library should carry a test for their attendants. He gives them some questioners to them. There are some questions relating with services. Those who are giving positive reaction to those the question considered him to for the counter.

In service sector there are very calm and positive mind peoples are requied. We see in various servicing sections they appointed staff like this.

In our modern libraries we provide all the facility to reader. For a librarian following are some qualities like:

- A deep study;
- A good reader;
- A good information Manager;
- User Friendly Behaviour;
- Know user needs;
- Spoken skills;
- Good in I.T. and also friendly to computer.
- Mostly giving Esteem to colleague.

Conclusion:

When we discuss the whole aspect of growth ratio, there is big and challenging thong is the management.

Management is the techniques where we go to the right goal. There are such big problems facing the goal. When we locate the right chart of working there is a chance to gain.

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